

The Kinetics of Reaction between Phenacyl Bromide and Aniline in Methyl and Iso-Amyl Alcohols

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The reaction of phenacyl bromide with aniline and its derivatives is a bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reaction. The values of Arrhenius parameters in the equation $k=Ae^{-E/RT}$ have been calculated for the reaction, which are found to be more or less constant throughout the series. The effect of the substituents in benzene nucleus of aniline has also been calculated and the additivity rule has been found to hold good for the series. The plots of specific rate constants of different reactions against the dipole moments of substituted anilines have been shown to be linear. The Hammett's equation also applies well to the reaction series.

The change of solvent from methyl to iso-amyl alcohol does not change the frequency factor; but a slight change is only observed in energy of activation.

The reaction between phenacyl bromide and aniline has been classified under the category of bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reaction. It was first studied by Cox¹ in benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, acetone, methyl, n-butyl- and benzylalcohols in dark. The rate of reaction was found to be fastest in methyl alcohol.

The values of probability factor 'P' calculated by Norrish and Smith² from the results obtained by Cox were found to increase with the increase in the polarity of the solvent. In the presence of large excess of aniline, Matheson and Hamphries³ found the reaction to be pseudo-unimolecular. Later on Baker^{4,5} observed the reaction in dry acetone and ethanol to follow the second order rate law, if the concentration of both aniline and phenacyl bromide were 0.025M.

However no reference is obtained about a systematic study regarding the effect of substituents of aniline on the kinetics of reaction between phenacyl bromide and aniline. This has been undertaken in the present study. The reaction has mainly been studied in methyl alcohol to find out

- (i) Variation of the energy of activation and frequency factor with the change of substituent groups in aniline.
- (ii) Relationship between the dissociation constants of different substituted aniline derivatives and their respective rate constants at a particular temperature.
- (iii) Effect of dipole moments of different substituted anilines on their energy of activation.
- (iv) Applicability of Hammett's equation in the reaction series.

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1. H. E. Cox, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 145.

2. G. W. Norrish and F. P. Smith, (1928), 129.

3. D. Matheson and J. E. Hamphries, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (1931), 1514.

4. J. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (1933), 1128.

5. J. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (1935), 184Q.

The reaction of phenacyl bromide with substituted anilines has also been studied in isoamyl alcohol to compare the values of energy of activation and frequency factor etc. with those obtained from the reaction in methyl alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and purification of materials: Methyl alcohol, AnalaR (E. Merck) was dried on lime and distilled at 64.5-65.5° iso-amyl alcohol, AnalaR (E. Merck) was distilled before use. The fraction between 113-114° was collected. Aniline (B.D.H.) was fractionated and the fraction boiling between 183.5-184° was collected. Substituted anilines were commercially supplied and purified either by distillation or by recrystallisation. The purified products had the following melting or boiling points:

Compound	M.P.	B.P.
<i>o</i> -chloro-aniline	—	208°
<i>m</i> -chloro-aniline	—	223°
<i>p</i> -chloro-aniline	70.5°	—
<i>o</i> -toluidine	—	199°
<i>m</i> -toluidine	—	203°
<i>p</i> -toluidine	45°	—
3-4-dichloro-aniline	71.5°	—
2-5 dimethyl-aniline	—	218°

Phenacyl bromide (*o*-bromo acetophenone) was prepared by the method given by Rather and Reid⁶. It was crystallised several times with hot alcohol, till white needle like crystals having melting point 50° were obtained.

PROCEDURE

The reaction of aniline with phenacyl bromide proceeds in the manner,

The hydrogen bromide formed was estimated after definite intervals of time.

In order to study the reaction kinetics (M/4) phenacyl bromide and (M/2) aniline solutions were prepared in methyl alcohol by weighing. 15 ml. of each of these solutions were kept in a constant temperature bath for twenty minutes and were then mixed together. The course of the reaction was followed by taking out 5ml. of reaction mixture at different intervals of time and mixed with 10ml. of (N/10) silver nitrate to precipitate the aniline hydrobromide. The excess of silver nitrate was estimated by titrating it with standard ammonium thiocyanate solution using ferric alum as indicator. The titre values lie within the accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$.

The specific rate constant was calculated by applying the bimolecular rate equation, suggested by Menachutkin⁷ and applied successfully by Peacock⁸ in calculating the bimolecular rate constant for the reaction between benzyl chloride and aniline. The thermostat was regulated to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Velocity constants were calculated at different temperatures ranging from 20-55°. The energy of activation was calculated by making use of 'least square method' and also from Arrhenius plots.

The experimental method followed in the case of iso-amyl alcohol was the same as in methyl alcohol.

The essential points for discussions are summarised in Table I & II.

TABLE I

The energy of activation and frequency factor at 40°C in methyl alcohol

S. No	Compound	$K_{40} \times 10^5$ l/mols./sec's	E cals./gm. mols	log PZ
1.	aniline	114.8	13360	6.4
2.	o-toluidine	30.9	14200	6.4
3.	m-toluidine	232.7	12700	6.2
4.	p-toluidine	495.4	11800	6.0
5.	o-chloro-aniline	3.4	16200	6.8
6.	m-chloro-aniline	12.6	15200	6.7
7.	p-chloro-aniline	31.0	14400	6.6
8.	3-4-dichloro aniline	5.5	15910	6.8
9.	2-5-dimethyl aniline	125.9	13860	6.8

TABLE II

The energy of activation and the frequency factor at 40°C in iso-amyl alcohol

S. No.	Compound	$K_{40} \times 10^5$ l/mols./sec's.	E cals./gm. mols	log PZ
1.	aniline	113.7	12800	6.7
2.	o-toluidine	53.7	14100	6.6
3.	m-toluidine	159.0	12500	5.9
4.	m-chloro-aniline	24.8	14400	6.5
5.	o-chloro-aniline	4.7	16000	6.8
6.	3-4-dichloro-aniline	14.1	15000	6.6

Constancy of frequency factor.

The plot of $\log k_{40}^\circ$ against the energy of activation is a straight line with a slope of -2.303 RT and the frequency factor is observed more or less constant. So the rate of reaction is dependent mainly on the energy of activation, changing with the nature of substituents. The average value of frequency factor for this reaction comes out to be 2.8×10^6 gm. mols. lit⁻¹ sec⁻¹ in methyl alcohol. However some compounds like 2-5 dimethyl aniline, p-methyl, o-chlor-, show frequency factor appreciably different from the average value, which may be attributed to the different degrees of solvation of

7. N.-Menschutkin, Z. Physik. Chem., 1890, 5, 589.

8. D. H. Peacock, J. Chem. Soc., 1924, 125, 1975.

the substituted anilines, as all the other factors involved in the equation according to collision theory,

$$Z = N^2 6^{-2} A_B 8 \pi RT (1/M_A + 1/M_B)^{1/2} C_A C_B$$

are remaining more or less constant for the reaction series.

Effect of substituents on energy of activation. From table I it is clear that meta- and para-methyl groups in benzene rings of aniline lower the energy of activation, whereas ortho-methyl group increases the activation energy presumably due to steric hindrance. When chloro group is substituted in place of methyl group, the energy of activation increases for all the compounds but the increase is much more marked for the ortho-position. The change in the rate of reaction is directly attributed to the variations in energy of activation. The values of ' ΔE ' for different groups for the reaction in methyl alcohol are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Substituent effect on the energy of activation

Group	Difference in E (ΔE).
o-methyl—	+840
m-methyl	-660
p-methyl—	-1560
o-chloro—	+2840
m-chloro—	+1840
p-chloro—	+1040

From these values the energies of activation for disubstituted derivatives have been calculated theoretically in order to test the validity of additive rule in the reaction studied. The values for 3-4-dichloro and 2-5-dimethyl aniline can be predicted in the following manner:

(i) Energy of activation of 3-4 dichloro aniline,

$$13360 + 1840 + 1040 = 16240 \text{ cal./gm.mols. Experimental value} = 15910 \text{ cal./gm. mols.}$$

(ii) Energy of activation of 2-5 dimethyl aniline,

$$13360 + 840 - 660 = 13540 \text{ cal./gm. mols. Experimental value} = 13860 \text{ cal./gm.mols.}$$

This agreement between the predicted and experimental values of activation energies confirms the validity of additivity rule in the reaction of phenacyl bromide with aniline.

Relation between reaction rate and dissociation constants of substituted anilines.

The plot of logarithm values of velocity constants for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with aniline and its different substituted derivatives, against the respective dissociation constant of the latter shows a linear relationship which can be explained from the fact that both the basic strength of anilines and their rates of

reactivity depend upon the availability of unshared pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom. The values of dissociation constants of aniline derivatives used here are given by Dippy⁹.

Relation between energy of activation and dipole moment. The activation energies for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with aniline and its derivatives in methyl alcohol are plotted against the dipole moment of substituted groups. A linear plot is obtained which is also anticipated, since the dipole moment is a measure of permanent displacement of electrons towards or away from the nucleus and reactivity of a nucleus depends upon the availability of unshared pair of electrons at the nitrogen atom.

Applicability of Hammett's equation. A reaction for the reactivity of meta- and para-substituted benzene derivatives has been established by Hammett.

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \rho \sigma$$

where k and k_0 are the velocity constants for the substituted and unsubstituted compounds respectively. The parameter (σ) characterises a particular substituent and (ρ) for the reaction series.

The reaction series fits in well with Hammett's equation. When (σ) for different substituents is plotted against $\log k_{40}^\circ$ for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with different meta- and para-substituted groups of anilines, a straight line with a slope of -2.87 is obtained. The negative value for the reaction series indicates that the reaction is made more difficult by electron withdrawal from the basic nitrogen atom of aniline. This is actually observed since substituted groups like NO_2 in aniline retard the reaction and the rate of reaction is so slow that it could not be studied.

Change of solvent from methyl to iso-amyl alcohol: It can easily be concluded from Table II that the effect of substituent in the benzene ring of aniline on reaction rate in iso-amyl alcohol is of the same order as in methyl alcohol. Further the change of solvent from methyl to iso-amyl alcohol does not affect the frequency factor but a slight change is observed only in activation energies.

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